

Relationship Between Zero and NonZero Rest Mass in Special Relativity

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 5, 2022

The Lorentz transformation was discovered by Lorentz by considering the invariance of Maxwell's electromagnetic equations as seen by a moving frame. These same equations yield a solution for a photon which shows its wavelike behaviour. Shortly after, Einstein obtained the same Lorentz transformations as well as energy-momentum ones by considering motion of a particle with rest mass together with motion by a photon. This led to the well-known nonzero rest mass equations $E=mc^2$, $E=m_0/\sqrt{1-(v/c)^2}$ and $p=Ev$ for a particle with a rest mass, but the transformation also applied to a photon although with a different dispersion relationship i.e. $E=pc$ (a classical wave relationship). About two decades later, de Broglie linked particle behaviour to photons and argued for a matter wave.

In previous notes (1) we argued that special relativity i.e. the Lorentz transformation may be derived strictly for a particle with rest mass without the need to include electromagnetic equations or photons. The result, however, includes a "special" constant velocity to allow for proper units. Furthermore this velocity is the same in all constant moving frames. In such an approach, this special velocity is not defined. Furthermore, $p=Ev$ and $E=m_0/\sqrt{1-(v/c)^2}$ so as $m_0 \rightarrow 0$ energy and momentum also tend to zero. There is, however, electrostatic energy and force associated with a charge which seems to have nothing to do with rest mass. Thus $p=Ev$ and nonzero rest mass cannot be the full picture it seems. In other words, for any (p,E) one wishes to use the same transformation, so there may be p,E pairs which do not correspond to a particle with nonzero rest mass. One might postulate a particle with momentum p which does not have a rest mass, but may still create impulse reactions within the electrostatic potential just as a particle with rest mass may create impulses. In such a case, the "special" single velocity might apply to this particle and it must be the same as viewed in any frame.

Given that the special velocity is already part of the special relativistic transformation developed for a particle with rest mass, one may argue that this transformation should contain two solutions, one for a nonzero rest mass particle and one for a zero rest mass one. In particular, one may find these using $dA=0$ where $A=-Et+px$ a Lorentz invariant. We have already argued this in previous notes. Given that special relativity contains solutions for both zero and nonzero rest mass particles and that zero rest mass particles exhibit wave properties, one may argue one should use this theory to argue for wave properties for a particle with nonzero rest mass we suggest. The difference is that for a particle with rest mass there is a special frame with m_0 , $x=0$ and $t=t_0$ such that x and t_0 (time) are decoupled. ($x=0$, and $t=t_0$) have already been shown to follow from any general (x,t) in $-Et+px$ in (1). A Lorentz transformation yields $x/t=v$ and one may show that $dA=0$ and that $-dE/dv x + dp/dv t = 0$ and $-E dt/dv + p dx/dv = 0$ separately. For the photon solution one may use $dA=0 = -Edt + pdx$. This couples t and x , but is also linked with a scaling time and length proportional to $1/E$ and $1/p$. For a photon these two are coupled to give the velocity. For a particle with rest mass, $1/E$ and $1/p$ are decoupled because the velocity follows from a Lorentz boost. Nevertheless $1/E$ and $1/p$ physically exist and delineate space and time, they just do not "create" velocity as in the photon case. Thus we argue that special relativity is really a dual theory describing both particles with and one special case without rest mass and that one has to consider the full set of similarities

between the two including scaling of x and t in $-Et+px$ which gives rise to “wave” type motion for both particles with rest mass and without.

Special Relativity and Nonzero Rest Mass

Newtonian mechanics was developed to describe particles with nonzero rest mass. Newton also considered photons to be particles which seems to imply they would have nonzero rest mass. (There are in fact articles in the literature which suggest that the photon might have a nonzero albeit tiny one like the neutrino.) Later wave properties of photons were discovered (1812-Young experiment) and then Maxwell developed his electromagnetic equations from experimental results. The solution of a photon resulted from these, but Newtonian mechanics was still the driving idea in dynamics. Thus it seems that when special relativity was developed, it was primarily a theory for describing how particles with nonzero rest mass behave. In particular, there are the celebrated results of Einstein $E=mc^2$, $E=m_0/\sqrt{1-(v^2/c^2)}$ and $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$. Einstein, however, used photons in his derivation of special relativistic transformations and so the speed of light in a vacuum c naturally appeared. Furthermore $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$ yields the photon result $E=pc$ if $m_0 \rightarrow 0$.

We suggest (as argued in (1) and other notes) that one may develop special relativistic results directly from considerations of a particle with nonzero rest mass. In such a case, the notion of a photon does not appear at all. A “strange” or “special” constant velocity parameter c , however, is needed to allow for dimensionless quantities i.e. v/c . In this approach it is not clear what c should be.

To begin we consider Newtonian mechanics which contains a quantity called momentum $= m_0 v$ and kinetic energy $.5m_0v^2$. We next consider a rest frame in which there is a mass m_0 , $v=0$ so $p=0$, $x=0$ and $t=t_0$. Thus x and t_0 are decoupled. We showed in (1) that any general (x,t) may be mapped to $x=0$, $t=t_0$ as $-Et+px$ (a Lorentz invariant as will be shown later) remains unchanged.

If the rest particle is viewed from a frame moving at $-v$, it will appear to move with velocity v . We assume that m_0 is proportional to energy, that it will transform to $E(v)$ and that there will be an energy flow of $E(v) v$. We consider a unitary type matrix, but the metric is not known as of yet. Then the transformation matrix is:

$$\begin{vmatrix} a & av \\ av & a \end{vmatrix} \quad ((1))$$

This yields: $E' = m_0 a$ and $p' = m_0 a v$ as well as: $x' = av t_0$ and $t' = t_0 a$

To fix the metric, one considers a general $(x,t_0) = (0,t_0) + (x,0)$ such that $(p',E') \cdot (x,0) = 0$. As shown in (1) there are two pieces: $p'x' = m_0 a v a v t_0$ and $E' t' = m_0 a t_0 a$. This combination must be 0 suggesting that one uses the metric yielding $-Et+px$ and $a = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ where c is an unknown parameter with units of velocity. Also v should be v/c in the above. Thus one may derive special relativity directly for a particle with rest mass with no considerations concerning a photon or electromagnetism. The question is: What is c , a single velocity which pertains to all frames? For example, if one has (p',E') ((1)) may be used a second

time to transform it to (p'', E'') , but the same c is used. It is a constant velocity parameter which has the same value in any frame.

It is interesting to note that if $m_0 \rightarrow 0$, then both E and p above go to 0. In other words energy and momentum disappear. Momentum may be thought of in terms of impulse hits i.e. $2p = \int F(t) dt$ in Newtonian mechanics. It may be noted that for a charged particle, two parameters m_0 and charge exist and each are related to energy and force (i.e. p is linked to force for a moving mass and there is electrostatic energy). If $m_0 \rightarrow 0$, charge energy is still present. Thus the above description which was developed for a particle with rest mass does not describe all energy, yet the vector (p, E) was used with ((1)). Given (p, E) how would one know that this only applies to momentum and energy linked to a rest mass? It would be good if it applied to all energy and momentum including the energy of a particle speculated to exist within an electrostatic potential. This particle has p and imparts impulse hits (which yield the electric field) (just like the impulse hits from a moving rest mass). If $m_0 \rightarrow 0$, its energy and momentum do not go to zero, yet they also transform according to ((1)) so one transformation theory applies to all momentum and energy. In such a case the unknown constant velocity parameter might describe such a particle. One must find information about such an object. We suggest considering the Lorentz invariant dot product $A = -Et + px$.

First consider a particle with rest mass m_0 such that $E = m_0 / \sqrt{1 - v^2}$ ($c=1$), $p = Ev$, $t = 1 / \sqrt{1 - v^2}$ and $x = vt_0 / \sqrt{1 - v^2}$. Then for $dA=0$ there are two pieces:

$$dA = 0 = \left\{ -\frac{dE}{dv} t + \frac{dp}{dv} x \right\} + \left\{ -E \frac{dt}{dv} + p \frac{dx}{dv} \right\} \text{ with } x/t = v$$

The first $\{$ is 0 so the second $\{$ must also be 0.

One may note that $A = -Et + px$ is of the form of scaling in other words $1/E$ scales time and $1/p$ scales x . A solution which keeps $dA=0$ is also $0 = -E dt + p dx$. This assumes that x and t are coupled i.e. change in a completely different way from the nonzero mass way $p=Ev$. In other words one has $dx/dt = v = E/p$. This would then describe the new particle with $v=c$. This particle would have the same velocity in all frames of reference as noted above. Furthermore $c=E/p$ is the solution for a classical wave. (It is already known from Maxwell's equations that light has a fixed speed c in a vacuum and follows $E=pc$ so the unknown particle in the electrostatic potential may be light i.e. a virtual photon.) It is already known that light has wavelike properties experimentally and these match the solution from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations which yield electric field = constant $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$. We argue that this wavelike behaviour is linked to the scaling of x by p and t by E .

Nonzero Rest Mass Particle and Wavelike Properties

In the above section we suggested one may obtain the Lorentz transformation matrix ((1)) by simply considering a particle with a nonzero rest mass. This leads to a result containing terms of the form v/c where c is a constant velocity parameter which is unknown. We argued that c pertains to a photon which has wavelike features linked to $A = -Et + px$ a Lorentz invariant. For a particle with nonzero rest mass E is not pv , but there is still scaling in A . In other words there is still a period proportional to $1/E$ and a wavelength proportional to $1/p$, but velocity is not given by

$E=pv$. There is, however, no reason not to expect some type of wavelike behaviour from the math form. Thus one has a particle which has nonzero rest mass, moves with v such that $p=Ev$, but contains wavelike behaviour associated with a decoupled period proportional to $1/E$ and a wavelength proportional to $1/p$. If v is constant velocity which is completely independent of the wave velocity $E=pc$, then it seems that one may use $\exp(iA)$ as a kind of probability to describe the particle with nonzero rest mass. $\exp(-iA) \exp(iA) = 1$ suggesting equal probability in space associated with $v=\text{constant}$ which is not a wave velocity. This overall spatial density is analogous to the term $\text{Electric field} * \text{Electric field}$ in the energy density of a photon. A wave has physical density, or energy density in the photon case changes, in space. Constant v for a plane wave $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ should not have these i.e. should be constant, yet there are still wave like features in the problem. We suggest decoupling $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ i.e. using $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ separately.

Thus the presence of a solution for a photon in $-Et+px$ i.e. in the Lorentz transformation (with terms v/c) also seems to impose wavelike properties (present in E scaling t and p scaling x) in $-Et+px$.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that one begins with a particle with nonzero rest mass and seeks a transformation which describes (p,E) and (x,t) as seen from a constant moving frame. The rest frame may be considered to have $(p=0, E=m_0)$ and $(x=0, t=t_0)$. A unitary type transformation of the form of ((1)) applies. If the dot product $(p,E) \cdot (x,t)$ is to be the same for $(0,t_0)$ and (x,t_0) then a special metric applies yielding the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$. It may be noted that in order to have dimensionless terms v/c , one must introduce a constant unknown velocity parameter c . This one velocity holds in all constant moving frames. It may also be noted that (p,E) should apply to all energy and momentum. If $m_0 \rightarrow 0$, p and E become 0, but a charged particle still has electrostatic energy under these conditions. If one postulates that there is an unknown particle with constant velocity c which has p and E which do not follow $p=Ev$, and that this new (p,E) should also transform according to ((1)), then one must identify this particle. Using $dA=0$ leads to two solutions. The first is $dA = dE/dv (-t) + dp/dv x - E dt/dv + p dx/dv$ and the second is $dA = -E dt + p dx$. In the first case, which describes a particle with rest mass, x and t are uncoupled in the rest frame i.e. $(0, t_0)$. In the second case, t and x are closely coupled and one finds the wave velocity $E=pv(\text{wave})$. Setting $v(\text{wave})=c$ pins down the unknown particle. One may note that $-Et+px$ also appears in the solution of a photon in Maxwell's theory so one may connect the two. It may be noted that one does not need to assume that c is the same in all frames, it follows directly from ((1)) because the same c parameter is used in all transformations i.e. one may transform $(0,m_0)$ to (p,E) and this involves c . Next, in this moving frame one uses another transformation to obtain (p',E') using the same value of c . Thus assuming a Lorentz transformation of the form ((1)) yields a solution for a photon. Even the wavelike features are present to a certain degree because $-Et+px$ contains scaling of t and p which leads to the idea of a frequency and wavelength. This same scaling and frequency and wavelength should apply to the particle with nonzero rest mass with the condition that $p=Ev$ and not $E=pv$. This means that the nonzero rest mass particle has a completely different velocity, but should still exhibit wavelike properties. A constant v independent of w (frequency) and wavelength suggests that a

free particle does not have an explicit real density (or energy density in the case of a photon) which behaves as $\cos(-\omega t+kx)\cos(-\omega t+kx)$. The solution $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, however, yields $\exp(iEt-ipx) \exp(-iEt+ipx) = 1$, but still contains wave behaviour.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Special Coordinates $v=x/t$, Special Relativity and Free Particle Actions (preprint, zenodo, 2022)